

The Portrait of Moralities In *The Scarlet Letter* by Nathaniel Hawthorne

Danul Aristiawan^{1*}

¹ Assistant Professor, Department of English, Stikes Yarsi Mataram, Mataram, Indonesia

*Corresponding author: danularisetiawan@gmail.com

Abstract

The aimed of this research was to analyze and describe about the morality in Nathaniel Hawthorne work entitled *The Portrait of morality in Scarlet Letter Novel* by Nathaniel Hawthorne. Specially ,this research deal with (1) What are the potrait of moralities by the main characters Hester Prynne ,Arthur Dimmsdale and Roger Chilingworth drawn in *Scarlet Letter Novel* (2) What are the sequences of these moralities for the main character as the doer of the moralities in *Scarlet Letter Novel*. This research was descriptive qualitative research. The data were words, phrases, sentences from the first chapter until the last chapter. Theories used used in this research were concerned with novel as a literary work, morals and ethics,morality,morality and religion,morality and law,immorality and the structural approach in literary criticism.This research was catagorized as literary criticms,where the researcher doing analysis, interpretation and evaluation in conducting the research.The writer applies the structural approach in hisresearchbecause to analyzes what moralities characters and what is the consequences of these moralities for the character's life based on the instrinsic element of this novel.The result of this research were stated as follow: (1)The moralities found in the *Scarlet Letter Novel* were adultery,hypocrisy and revenge (2)The three main characters get different consequences of thier morality and face the risk of the morality in different ways.Finally the author can conclude that no one is perfect even the priest which supposed tobe the right hand of God.This novel reveal the morality in details and the important point is how this novel is relevant for generation to generation as a guidebook in morality aspect in society.And the writer advise that the next writer will write about literary criticism in different point of view.

Keywords: potrait of moralities, characters, novel

1. INTRODUCTION

Literature is a description of life and bring so many moral values for the society as the reflection of their life which affected one to another. Novel is one example of literature work which designed beautifully and artistically through words in detail. By this work readers can internalize the moments, event and the expression of heart and mind in it. Literary work is a human being thought tell emotion field. This work also delivered interesting things to developed our knowledge dealing with literary works. Glickberg in Endraswara (2008:77) states that “all literature, although fantastic or mystical issues, is animated strongly social concern, we can say that literary works can give something imaginative things in our life. It means that literature is one of human imagination and experiences which is designed with full moral values for human life.

If someone read a literary work such as novel, they have connection on value delivered by the novel itself. Everyone has different point of view in interpret, analyze and see the meaning of literary works. Reader with out of expectation will give different of meaning to a certain literary work. On this situation which connected to characteristic and realty problems of the literary work.

History:

Received : 26 November 2023

Revised : 14 March 2024

Accepted : 11 April 2024

Published : 30 April 2024

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11649478](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11649478)

Website: www.sanskritjournal.com

Publisher: Siksha O Anusandhan

License: This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/)

Wellek and Warren, (1993:18-20) states that the characteristics of literary works can be shown by several aspects including fiction, creation, and imaginative. However, literary works can function as ideological depending on the point of view and are determined by their ideological background. Literary works stand on an innovation and also the conventions of the local community. This is what makes literary works a comprehensive study in the elaboration of a literary work. This explanation provides deep value for a writer of literary works in order to provide useful benefits for readers of literary works.

In addition, it also contains of education value. One of the examples is a novel which bring some values for the reader to understand their message conveyed by the author. In another way literary work could be a source for readers as their need, interest, cultural background, and language levels. Most of people are interested with literary work like novel, drama or poetry because some of the reason which related with life, love, happiness and sorrow.

According Untoro (2007: 6) stated that linguistic has something to contribute to literary criticism, just a literary criticism contributes something to linguistics. There is a link between linguistics and literature, it is called stylistic. Stylistic has a connection or link to relate between disciplines: linguistics and literary criticism, between subjects: language and literature and between discipline and subjects: linguistics and literary criticism and language. Meanwhile, Carter in Untoro (2007;2) stated that consider studying literary works from a linguistics point of view as a stylistic practice that is process of literary text analysis is started with an assumption that the main interpretation procedure used in literary text reading is linguistic procedure.

The novel has something that is very closely related to the nature or character of the author. A novel is usually a character possessed by a person or individual with his personality. In a literary work, the storyline of a novel is a series of events related to the events that occur in a novel and it is arranged by a writer. The author writes a literary work or novel based on real events in one's life. Basically, the novel talks about a person's life in interaction with society and these are real events experienced by a writer. The characters that appear in a literary work or novel are usually taken from real characters, but some are taken from fantasy characters. Even though the novel is considered a fantasy story, the events or events and characters that appear in a literary work must be believed because they often occur in everyday life. A novel must be credible or can be trusted. The uniqueness in a novel, the author leads the reader to guess the continuation of the novel's story. Many novels are written in a style or method that leaves the reader unsettled and full of tension or unresolved questions. The curiosity that arises from a reader to find out the ending of a novel makes the writer's ability to design a story that is difficult to predict. In other words, a good novel can arouse the reader's deep curiosity: they stimulate one's thinking or the "feel good" elements in novels make readers play them over and over in their minds to lighten the load. "Feel good" moments again and again. By reading a literary work or novel is something that can fill leisure time that can be happy and enjoyable. By reading a novel one can stop for a moment to let go of all the hustle and bustle of daily activities.

2. METHOD

To collect the data, there are some steps that the researcher does. First, the researcher did intensive and analytical reading in novel *The Scarlet Letter* to get more understanding. Second, researcher continue to selecting the content of the novel that reflects to the objective of the study that is about the immoralities in the novel by underlying the words or sentences that reflect to the analysis. Third, he classifies the require data to answer the statements of the problems correctly. The last step was evaluating the appropriate data.

After collecting the data and study the information taken from many literary books closely related to this study, the researcher began to analyze them by following these steps. First, identifying the data related to the problems of the study. Second, organizing and separating the data, thus only the required ones are quoted and analyzed based on the objectives of study, they are: (1) to know what is the portrait of moralities by the main characters in *The Scarlet Letter* Novel by Nathaniel Hawthorne (2) to know what are the implication in daily life of these moralities for the main characters as the doers in *The Scarlet Letter* Novel by Nathaniel Hawthorne. Third, doing deep analysis and interpretation on the data deals with problems of this study, and then reviewing and determining each event that supports the study. The last step is drawing conclusion and rechecking if the conclusion is appropriate enough to answer the stated problems.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

When someone around does something that is not in accordance with our way, then we will see that someone is a little less than us. So that we cannot criticize or give suggestions of the "imperfections" we see before us. Imperfection or lack of a person can be a way to give in to certain conditions and. When Hester openly had a negative stigma as an adulterer, the people around them began to think of other people as bad people. He became a symbol that the world of his actions had damaged his social life and caused damage to his mental and physical happiness.

"But the point which drew all eyes, and, as it were, transfigured the wearer -- so that both men and women who had been familiarly acquainted with Hester Prynne were now impressed as if they beheld her for the first time -- was that Scarlet Letter, so fantastically embroidered and illuminated upon her bosom. It had the effect of a spell, taking her out of the ordinary relations with humanity, and enclosing her in a sphere by herself." (The Scarlet Letter, 61)

If we can all accept the fact that no one is perfect in this world, then why can't we accept the fact that there are imperfect people in this world? The punishment meted out to Hester not only shatters her life, but visually shows the sins of all those around her who question her innocence. Arthur Dimmesdale, Hester's partner in adultery, is a minister, one whom the people look up to for guidance and direction. The people consider him almost sinless, the perfect model which to follow. The townspeople thought of him as:

"a true priest, a true religionist, with the reverential sentiment largely developed, and an order of mind that impelled itself powerfully along the track of creed" (The Scarlet Letter, 122)

Will a Dimmesdale feel he has committed an act that is included in a grave sin, namely adultery, as a sense of Dimmesdale's responsibility, he declares himself to step down from his position as a clergyman or confess all the sinful acts he has committed to the public and society. Or even vice versa, where Dimmesdale will hide his sins and not admit his actions and reveal

Hester's sins in his sermon. A "true minister" would not hide his sinful acts from his audience, as Dimmesdale did. The fact that Dimmesdale had hidden all his own sinful deeds while explaining the sins of other people, namely Hester's sins, which were actually the same, so that made Dimmesdale a hypocrite. How can someone be punished when the people around him also do the same thing. How can we give punishment for the act of adultery? Where the community at that time considered the act of adultery to be an act that violated ethics rather than harming society. When someone commits adultery, only the person involved is involved because it is very personal. The fact that the church has so much influence over government itself is not in the best interests of society, and crimes against God's will are not necessarily crimes against mankind. Every character is in some degree, a hypocrite. The townspeople and officials are because of their views of Hester and how they treat her. The people that they are and the people that they are become through the circumstances of their situation show this.

Be not silent from any mistaken pity and tenderness for him; for, believe me, Hester, though he were to step down from a high place, and stand there beside thee, on thy pedestal of shame, yet better were it so, than to hide a guilty heart through life. What can thy silence do for him, except it tempt him--yea, compel him, as it were--to add hypocrisy to sin?" (The scarlet Letter, Pg.26)

Hester asks Dimmesdale to go public with everything that happened and to tell him who she was committing adultery with. He asked not to be a hypocrite, it would seriously damage his good name and dignity as a religious leader. However, even though he had made such suggestions, Dimmesdale, with his firm determination, did not want to open himself up to tell everything that happened to the public. What is the public's view regarding this matter, will Hester respond to Dimmesdale's request at this time with, where He is the child of a prominent religious leader Arthur Dimmesdale.

Would not the people start up in their seats, by a simultaneous impulse, and tear him down out of the pulpit which he defiled? Not so, indeed! They heard it all, and did but reverence him the more. They little guessed what deadly purport lurked in those self-condemning words. "The godly youth!" said they among themselves. "The saint on earth! (The Scarlet Letter, Pg.7)

But in the end Dimmesdale bravely told all of his deeds to his congregation implicitly and his congregation could not believe what Dimmesdale had done. He also said that he was a bad person, irresponsible, sinful. However, this statement expressed by Dimmesdale made him a more dignified and responsible person in the eyes of his people. The actions he took by admitting all his actions made him a good person in the eyes of his society. With all his humility made him a role model for his congregation. If Dimmesdale doesn't tell all the events that happened then that will make him a figure who is no longer a role model.

Nay; not so, my little Pearl!" answered the minister; for, with the new energy of the moment, all the dread of public exposure, that had so long been the anguish of his life, had returned upon him; and he was already trembling at the conjunction in which—with a strange joy, nevertheless—he now found himself. "Not so, my child. I shall, indeed, stand with thy mother thee one other day, but not to-morrow!" (The scarlet Letter, Pg. 17-28)

Someone's behavior that has been symbolized by actions that violate ethics is deviant behavior. He nailed Dimmesdale's hypocrisy on the nose. We see in this moment why the Pastor is caught up in the hypocrisy: he is genuinely afraid of "public exposure". He's a bit of a coward, isn't he? Especially when we consider Hester's suffering. How could Pearl be so

smart? Does he have x-ray vision or something? If Pearl's character were removed from the story completely, how would the story change?

No, Hester, no!" replied the clergyman. "There is no substance in it! It is cold and dead, and can do nothing for me! Of penance I have had enough! Of penitence there has been none! Else, I should long ago have thrown off these garments of mock holiness, and have shown myself to mankind as they will see me at the judgment-seat. Happy are you, Hester, which wear the Young Goodman Brown openly upon your bosom! Mine burns in secret! Thou little know what a relief it is, after the torment of a seven years' cheat, to look into an eye that recognizes me for what I am!" (The scarlet Letter, Pg.18)

Hypocrisy is more difficult to forgive, or to heal from, than a sin that is aired out in the open Hester is a round, major character and a protagonist in this novel. She comes from Old England. She marries Dr. Prynne, an old educated man who spends most of his time on science. However, she does not love him. Hester lives in New England, Boston, while her husband is still in Amsterdam.....Yonder woman, Sir, you must know, was the wife of a certain learned man, English by birth, but who had long ago dwelt in Amsterdam, whence some good time ago he was minded to cross over and cast in his lot with us of the Massachusetts. To this purpose he sent his wife before him, remaining himself to look after some necessary affairs.

Marry, good Sir, in some two years, or less, that the woman has been a dweller here in Boston, no tidings have come of this learned gentleman, Master Prynne; and his young wife, look you, being left to her own misguidance-- (The Scarlet Letter, Pg.68)

Hester Prynne has shocked the Puritans of Boston by committing adultery. Two years before the opening of the story, she is sent to America alone by her husband to await his coming. As far as the world knows, Hester's husband, Dr. Prynne (an elderly scientist) has disappeared. All of Boston is anxious for Hester to tell the name of her secret lover, the father of her child named Pearl. The immoralities which are done by Hester Prynne are adultery, hypocrisy, and also revenge. Between three of the main characters who did immoralities, Hester is the one who show her guilty feeling and try to do whatever the human being do although the society cannot receive her as the member of this society. Hester Prynne has strength of character. She is very honest so she openly acknowledges her sin. Hester stands on the scaffold, exposed to public humiliation, and wears a The Scarlet Letter her dress for the rest of her life as a sign of shame. Her beauty and warmth go away, buried under the burden of the elaborate of *The Scarlet Letter* her bosom. Hester settles in a cottage at the edge of town, lives a somber life with her daughter, and earns a living with her needlework. She has to bear the contempt of the townspeople and she has nothing but her strength of spirit to sustain her.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on research finding and data discussions in previous chapter, the researcher concludes that the moral values found in the story "The Scarlet Letter" are positive and negative moral value. The moral values that show in the story are lover, wise, care, responsibility, regret and self-confidence. Beside positive moral value in the story also has a negative moral value. The negative moral values there are arrogant, greedy, gripe and avaricious. It's a bad attitude that not allows we take. Arrogant, avaricious and greedy will destroy what we have, and when all this happens, can only regret that. Whereas, gripe attitude is the attitude of a slacker who just wants everything instantly without hard work. The novel "The Scarlet Letter" give us many

lessons about moral, especially positive and negative moral value. The moral values which are discovered in the novel "The Scarlet Letter". The novel touch us how to be a good person by have a positive moral value. The story has implications in the education. The students can learn and practice those positive moral values in their daily life. Therefore, by reading the short story they not only get the entertainment but also moral messages which are implied in the story. Moreover, story can be used as a media in education. Narrative text of literary works is suitable to be a media to teach English. This novel contains many technical words which can improve students' vocabulary. Using literature as a media to teach English can develop critical and creative thinking of the students by letting them make an analysis of a literary works. Narrative text The Scarlet Letter can be applied in English Language Teaching.

5. REFERENCES

- Abrams, M.H. 1981. "A Glossary Literary Terms". New York: Holt, Rinehart, and Winston Inc.
- Endraswara, Suwardi. 2008. "Metodologi Penelitian Sastra: Epistemologi, Model, Teori, dan Aplikasi." Yogyakarta: Media Pressindo
- Hawthorne, N. 1959. "The Young Good Man". A Novel. The New American Library, New York and Toronto
- Hawthorn, Jeremy. 1989. "Studying the Novel: An Introduction". New York: Routledge, Chapman, and Hall
- Hornby, A.S. 1995. "Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Current English". Great Oxford University Press
- Kenney, William. 1966. "How to Analyze Fiction". New York: Monarch Press
- Kholil, Masrukhin. 2007. "An Analysis on the Internal Conflicts Faced by Main Characters of Nathaniel"
- Koten, Thomas. Hukum dan Moral, Sebuah Seruan Etis. Accessed on 10 January 2013 from <http://www.suarapembaruan.com/News/2001/10/20/Editor/ed05.htm>
- Miller, J Hillis. 2005. "Literature as Conduct". Speech Act in Henry James. New York: Fordham University Press
- Myyry, Liisa. 2003. "Components Morality". of A Professional ethics: perspective on Moral motivation, moral sensitivity, moral reasoning, and related construct among University students. A Dissertation. Faculty of Social Sciences of the University of Helsinki.
- Swales, John M & Christine B. Feak. 1994. "Academic Writing for Graduate Students". Essential Task and Skills. Michigan: University of Michigan Press